

Broadband Microwave Frequency Measurement Using a Heterogeneous Multicore Fiber

Elham Nazemosadat
ITEAM Research Institute
Universitat Politècnica de València
Valencia, Spain
sbnazars@iteam.upv.es

Sergi García
ITEAM Research Institute
Universitat Politècnica de València
Valencia, Spain
sergarc3@iteam.upv.es

Ivana Gasulla
ITEAM Research Institute
Universitat Politècnica de València
Valencia, Spain
ivgames@iteam.upv.es

Abstract—We experimentally demonstrate a microwave frequency measurement scheme using a heterogeneous multicore fiber (MCF). Taking advantage of the inherently different differential group delays (DGDs) among four cores of the heterogeneous MCF, two individual 2-tap microwave filters with different free spectral ranges (FSRs) are constructed and the power ratio between their frequency responses is used as the amplitude comparison function (ACF). Since the DGD among the cores and the FSR of the filters are wavelength-dependent, by tuning the operational wavelength over a set of different values, we can obtain a set of different ACF traces. The collective information provided by these ACFs is then used to estimate the unknown frequency. Compared to many previous microwave frequency measurement approaches using dispersive elements, this scheme offers higher flexibility, tunability and compactness, along with higher measurement resolution (± 71 MHz) over a broader radiofrequency range (0.5-40 GHz).

Index Terms—Microwave photonics, microwave frequency measurement, multicore fibers, optical delay lines, space division multiplexing.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microwave frequency measurement is crucial for various applications, such as electronic warfare, anti-stealth defense and electronic intelligence systems [1] and has also gained interest in wireless high-speed communication systems [2]. Since electrical-based frequency measurement systems are limited in terms of their speed and frequency measurement range and are vulnerable to electromagnetic interference, photonic-based microwave frequency measurement approaches have become attractive in the past decades as they can overcome these limitations and offer wide operating bandwidth, high speed, low loss, and immunity to electromagnetic interference [3]. In photonic-based microwave frequency measurement systems, the unknown frequency is mapped to another parameter that can be measured in a straightforward manner, such as the optical or microwave power [4]–[7]. To reduce the effect of probable fluctuations in these parameters on the frequency estimation, it is common to map the frequency to a power ratio known as the amplitude comparison function (ACF). The ACF is the power ratio of two different optical or electrical signals that contain information about the unknown frequency and can be obtained using different approaches, including, among others, the nonlinear stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS)

effect [7], four-wave mixing [8], or using a dispersive element to either implement the fiber chromatic dispersion-induced power fading effect [4]–[6] or construct microwave photonic filters [9]. Given the periodic nature of ACF curves obtained in dispersive media, unique mapping between the measured power and the unknown frequency is possible only in a single monotonic interval of the ACF. Beyond that interval, each measured power value could respond to multiple frequency solutions and lead to ambiguities in the frequency estimation. Consequently, for approaches based on dispersive elements, the reported frequency measurement bandwidths are limited to around 20 GHz, with typical measurement errors of 100-200 MHz. This limitation can be solved by using multiple ACFs instead of one [10], [11], where the extra information provided by the additional ACFs can be used to identify the correct frequency solution among all possible solutions. Thus, since the unknown RF frequency can be estimated unambiguously beyond a single monotonic interval of the ACF, the measurement bandwidth is broadened using this method.

In this work, a microwave frequency measurement approach based on a heterogeneous multicore fiber (MCF) is proposed and experimentally demonstrated, where the unknown frequency is estimated over a broad bandwidth using multiple ACFs. The ratio between the frequency responses of a pair of microwave photonic filters with different free-spectral ranges (FSRs) are used to construct each of the ACFs, while each filter is implemented using two different cores of the heterogeneous MCF. In recent years, it has been shown that space division multiplexing (SDM) in MCFs and few-mode fibers can be applied to microwave photonics, where the different group delays of the different optical paths (cores/modes) within these fibers are used to construct tunable optical sampled true-time delay lines [12]–[14]. Using SDM fibers in microwave photonics applications is attractive as they offer increased compactness due to their inherent parallelism, performance flexibility and versatility. Additionally, these fibers could provide fiber-distributed signal processing without requiring a dedicated system external to the fiber, which is particularly of interest to radio access networks for 5G and Beyond.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup of the demonstrated heterogeneous MCF-based frequency measurement scheme. BS: broadband source, EDFA: erbium-doped fiber amplifier, IM: intensity modulator, VDL: variable delay line, VOA: variable optical attenuators, PD: photodetector, VNA: vector network analyser.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION

In our proposed scheme, shown in Fig. 1, an optical signal is modulated by the unknown microwave signal and launched into 4 cores of a heterogeneous MCF. Two cores are combined and detected jointly using a photodetector (PD), and the same is done for the other two cores. In core n of a MCF, the group delay τ_n at a given optical wavelength λ , can be expanded in a first-order Taylor series around an anchor wavelength λ_0 , given by [12]:

$$\tau_n(\lambda) = [\tau_{0,n} + (\lambda - \lambda_0)D_{0,n}]L, \quad (1)$$

where $\tau_{0,n}$ and $D_{0,n}$ represent the group delay per unit length and chromatic dispersion of core n at the anchor wavelength, respectively, while L is the fiber length. Given that the heterogeneous cores have distinct group delays, their differential group delay (DGD), expressed as $\Delta\tau$, can be used to implement 2-tap microwave signal filters by combining the output of any two cores and detecting them together [3]. Thus, in our scheme, two distinct 2-tap microwave signal filters are constructed using the 4 cores, where the DGD among the two cores constructing the first filter is $\Delta\tau_1$ and that of the second filter is $\Delta\tau_2$. The FSR of filter j , where $j = \{1, 2\}$, is $\text{FSR}_j = 1/\Delta\tau_j$, while the microwave power detected at the output of the filter is $P_j \propto \cos^2(\pi f_{RF} \Delta\tau_j)$, where f_{RF} is the unknown microwave frequency. The ACF, defined as the ratio between these two detected powers, is given by

$$\text{ACF} = \frac{P_1}{P_2} = \frac{\cos^2(\pi f_{RF} \Delta\tau_1)}{\cos^2(\pi f_{RF} \Delta\tau_2)}. \quad (2)$$

Since Eq. 2 has a periodic behavior, a unique mapping between the measured ACF value and the unknown RF frequency is only possible for a monotonic interval of the ACF, whose frequency range is determined by the smallest FSR_j or the largest $\Delta\tau_j$. Thus, ideally to increase the frequency measurement range, the ACF should have a broad monotonic interval. However, the measurement resolution becomes relatively low in large monotonic intervals. To solve this issue and increase both the measurement bandwidth and resolution, instead of using a single ACF with a broad monotonic interval, we use the collective information provided by multiple different ACFs with narrower monotonic intervals to determine the unknown frequency. Since the DGD between the cores depends on the optical wavelength, we propose

tuning the optical wavelength to vary $\Delta\tau_1$ and $\Delta\tau_2$ values and consequently obtain multiple ACFs. In this case, first the ACF values for a given set of operational wavelengths, over a specific microwave frequency bandwidth, are measured and stored in a reference look-up table. Then, once an unknown microwave signal is received, the powers at the output of the filters are measured at each of those operational wavelengths, and their ratios are calculated. This measured power ratio is compared against the look-up table associated with each wavelength and the potential solutions for each ACF curve are found. The intersection of the potential solutions found from the different ACF curves is selected as the unknown frequency.

III. 7-CORE HETEROGENEOUS MCF

A 5-km dispersion-tailored 7-core heterogeneous MCF is used in this work, where each of its step-index GeO₂-doped silica cores is surrounded by a pure silica inner cladding and a 1%-Fluorine-doped trench [13]. The MCF was originally designed to operate as a tunable optical sampled true-time delay line, which requires $\Delta\tau$ among neighboring cores to (a) be constant and (b) have a linear behavior with the optical wavelength [12]. The designed and measured DGDs of the cores with respect to core 7 are depicted in Fig. 2,

Fig. 2. DGDs of all MCF cores with respect to core 7. The inset depicts the SEM image of the fabricated heterogeneous MCF.

where a good agreement between the theory and experimental measurements is seen for cores 3 to 7. The two smallest cores (cores 1 and 2) have been affected by fabrication errors, leading to the discrepancy observed between their designed and measured DGD values. At the anchor wavelength $\lambda_0 = 1530$ nm, the slight mismatches between the group delays of the cores are compensated using variable optical delay lines (VDLs), such that $\Delta\tau = 0$ is obtained at this wavelength. For cores 3 to 7, there is a constant $\Delta\tau$ among neighboring cores for $\lambda > \lambda_0$; thus, $\Delta\tau$ between cores 5 and 7 is twice that of cores 3 and 4. Correspondingly, we used the outputs of cores 3 and 4, with a DGD of $\Delta\tau_1$, and the outputs of cores 5 and 7, with a DGD of $\Delta\tau_2 = 2\Delta\tau_1$, to construct the two 2-tap filters required for our scheme. The chromatic dispersion values of cores 3 to 7 increase from 16.6 to 20.6 ps/km/nm at 1530 nm, respectively, in constant steps of $\Delta D = 1$ ps/km/nm.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The frequency measurement experimental setup is displayed in Fig. 1. To avoid optical coherent interference, the input optical signal is a broadband source followed by a 0.1-nm-bandwidth optical filter. After amplification, the optical signal is launched into an intensity modulator driven by a microwave signal generated by a vector network analyser (VNA), whose RF frequency varies from 10 MHz up to 40 GHz. The carrier suppression effect is avoided by applying single sideband modulation. A fan-in device is used to inject the modulated signal into cores 3, 4, 5 and 7 of the 7-core MCF. The average insertion loss of the cores and the average crosstalk among them at the MCF output, including the fan-in/fan-out devices, are 5.8 dB and below -40 dB, respectively. After the 5-km MCF, the slight mismatches between the core group delays at the anchor wavelength are compensated using VDLs, similar to Fig. 2. Then, to obtain uniform amplitude distribution, the core output powers are equalized using variable optical attenuators (VOAs). The two 2-tap filters are constructed and the ratio of the power detected at the output of these filters is used as the ACF. By adjusting the optical filter and sequentially setting the optical wavelength to 1550, 1552, 1557 and 1560 nm, we obtain $\Delta\tau_1$ values of 100, 110, 135 and 150 ps, respectively. The ACF curves at each of these wavelengths are measured ten times and their averages, shown in Fig. 3, are stored in a look-up table.

The performance of our proposed scheme in estimating unknown frequencies is evaluated by sweeping the microwave frequency applied to the modulator from 0.5 to 40 GHz in 0.5-GHz steps and at each step, the operational wavelength is successively set to 1550, 1552, 1557 and 1560 nm. For each wavelength, the ratio of the two microwave powers, detected by the two PDs, is calculated and compared with the particular ACF curve of the look-up table (Fig. 3) that corresponds to that wavelength. Then, all frequencies in the look-up ACF that have the same value as the measured power ratio are appointed as potential solutions of that ACF curve. The intersection of the potential solutions of the four ACF curves is chosen as the unknown frequency. Given the broad measurement bandwidth

Fig. 3. ACFs measured at different wavelengths, with different $\Delta\tau_1$ and $\Delta\tau_2 = 2\Delta\tau_1$ values. The dashed lines indicate the power ratio corresponding to 18 GHz for each of the ACF curves, while the dots show all the potential frequency solutions. The shaded blue areas show that while the intersection of the potential solutions of the first 3 ACF curves leads to 2 frequencies (18 GHz and around 33 GHz), the intersection of all 4 ACF curves has only one solution (18 GHz). Therefore, all 4 ACF curves are required to correctly estimate the unknown frequency.

(40 GHz), we need 4 ACF curves to be able to retrieve all the frequencies within this bandwidth with a small error. As shown in Fig. 3, using fewer number of ACF curves could lead to notable measurement errors for some frequencies.

The microwave frequency estimated by the proposed scheme versus the applied input frequency is shown in blue in Fig. 4(a), while the residual error is displayed in green, for five sets of measurements. The residual error is below ± 71 MHz while the maximum root-mean square (rms) error, shown in Fig. 4(b), is 44 MHz within 0.5-40 GHz. The sources contributing to this error could be the amplified spontaneous emission noise of the amplifier, the bias drift of the modulator, the thermal noise from the PDs or the VNA, which lead to slight jitters in the notch frequencies of the microwave photonic filters and change the ACF. These results show a considerable two-fold improvement in terms of measurement bandwidth as compared to previous frequency measurement reports using dispersive delay elements [5], [6], [9]–[11], which to the best of our knowledge in the best scenario had errors of up to ± 90 MHz over a 19.5-GHz frequency range [11]. Even though the measurement accuracy of our

Fig. 4. (a) Estimated frequency versus the input frequency shown with blue (left axis) and the corresponding measured residual error shown with green dots (right axis). (b) The root-mean square error calculated for each input frequency.

scheme is not as good as some relatively more complex schemes based on optical nonlinear effects [7], [8], we believe it could be further improved by increasing the ACF curve slopes through increasing the $\Delta\tau$ values. Different approaches could be used to implement this, such as decreasing the anchor wavelength through proper adjustment of the VDLs, increasing the MCF length or using a different set of cores with larger DGDs to construct the microwave filters. For example, one filter could be constructed using cores 4 and 6, and the other using cores 3 and 7, which would double the $\Delta\tau$ values of this work.

V. CONCLUSIONS

We present an experimental demonstration of a frequency measurement scheme based on a heterogeneous MCF. Using the differential group delays between four cores of the MCF, two tunable 2-tap microwave filters with different free spectral ranges are constructed. The ratio between the frequency responses of these two filters is used as the amplitude comparison function. The FSRs of the two filters are tuned by changing the optical operational wavelength and consequently several different ACF curves are obtained. The complementary information provided by the different ACFs is then used to estimate the unknown frequency. A residual error of

± 71 MHz (root-mean square error of 44 MHz) is achieved in a measurement range of 0.5–40 GHz, which is a significant improvement, particularly in terms of measurement bandwidth, compared to previous reports using dispersive elements. This work extends the variety of microwave signal processing applications that can be implemented using a heterogeneous MCF.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Research Council (Consolidator Grant Project 724663), Generalitat Valenciana Advanced Instrumentation for World Class Microwave Photonics Research (IDIFEDER/2018/031) and Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación (PID2020-118310RB-100).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. L. Adamy, *Introduction to Electronic Warfare Modeling and Simulation; 1st ed.* SciTech, 2006.
- [2] C. R. Stevenson, G. Chouinard, Z. Lei, W. Hu, S. J. Shellhammer, and W. Caldwell, "IEEE 802.22: The first cognitive radio wireless regional area network standard," *IEEE Commun. Mag.*, vol. 47, no. 1, pp. 130–138, 2009.
- [3] R. Minasian, "Photonic signal processing of microwave signals," *IEEE Trans. Microw. Theory Techn.*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 832–846, 2006.
- [4] L. Nguyen and D. Hunter, "A photonic technique for microwave frequency measurement," *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 18, no. 10, pp. 1188–1190, 2006.
- [5] X. Zou and J. Yao, "An optical approach to microwave frequency measurement with adjustable measurement range and resolution," *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 20, no. 23, pp. 1989–1991, 2008.
- [6] J. Zhou, S. Fu, S. Aditya, P. P. Shum, and C. Lin, "Instantaneous microwave frequency measurement using photonic technique," *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 21, no. 15, pp. 1069–1071, 2009.
- [7] H. Jiang, D. Marpaung, M. Pagani, K. Vu, D.-Y. Choi, S. J. Madden, L. Yan, and B. J. Eggleton, "Wide-range, high-precision multiple microwave frequency measurement using a chip-based photonic Brillouin filter," *Optica*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 30–34, Jan 2016.
- [8] H. Emami, M. Ashourian, and M. Ebnali-Heidari, "Dynamically reconfigurable all optical frequency measurement system," *J. Lightw. Technol.*, vol. 32, no. 24, pp. 4796–4802, 2014.
- [9] X. Zou, W. Pan, B. Luo, and L. Yan, "Dispersion-induced-loss-independent photonic instantaneous frequency measurement using remote-fiber-based tunable microwave filter," *IEEE Photon. Technol. Lett.*, vol. 22, no. 15, pp. 1090–1092, 2010.
- [10] B. Vidal, "Photonic-based instantaneous microwave frequency measurement with extended range," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 284, no. 16, pp. 3996–3999, 2011.
- [11] N. Shi, Y. Gu, J. Hu, Z. Kang, X. Han, and M. Zhao, "Photonic approach to broadband instantaneous microwave frequency measurement with improved accuracy," *Opt. Commun.*, vol. 328, pp. 87–90, 2014.
- [12] I. Gasulla and J. Capmany, "Microwave photonics applications of multicore fibers," *IEEE Photon. J.*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 877–888, 2012.
- [13] S. García, M. Ureña, and I. Gasulla, "Demonstration of distributed radiofrequency signal processing on heterogeneous multicore fibres," in *Proceedings of 45th European Conference on Optical Communication (ECOC 2019)*, pp. 1–4.
- [14] E. Nazemosadat and I. Gasulla, "Dispersion-tailored few-mode fiber design for tunable microwave photonic signal processing," *Opt. Express*, vol. 28, no. 24, pp. 37 015–37 025, Nov 2020.